

Strategic Competitor Analysis for Market Re-entry: The Case of PT. Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the strategic marketing framework and its impact on the business growth of PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera, an architectural firm in Bogor. It specifically analyzes the interior design company industry over five years (2018-2023), focusing on two service lines: interior design only, and a combination of interior design and architecture. The research employs a qualitative approach. The data reveals a peak in project numbers in 2018, followed by a significant decline in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which resulted in prolonged stagnation in sales. A detailed competitor analysis highlights a substantial gap in digital presence, with competitors achieving higher engagement through effective use of social media platforms. The study outlines strategic recommendations for PT Primacon to enhance its digital marketing efforts, including leveraging social media analytics, increasing interactive content, and collaborating with influencers. Additionally, it emphasizes the need for improved sales management practices to adapt to evolving consumer preferences. Integrating e-commerce capabilities to showcase and sell design services or custom furniture could streamline client engagement and broaden market reach. Embracing sustainable design trends could also position Primacon. Gallery is a pioneer in environmentally conscious architecture and interior design, appealing to the growing demographic of eco-conscious consumers. Additionally, diversifying into corporate and commercial projects could unlock new revenue streams and diversify the company's market presence. Nevertheless, Primacon. Gallery must navigate several threats. The increasing competition from influencers offering lower-priced services could erode its market share among budget-conscious clients. Economic downturns could dampen client spending on premium design services, impacting revenue streams. The rapid pace of technological advancements in design software necessitates continuous investment in training and technology upgrades to maintain its competitive edge. Moreover, market saturation in the interior design sector could make it challenging to distinguish itself from competitors offering similar services. Shifts in client preferences towards new architectural and design trends could require significant adjustments in service offerings and expertise, demanding ongoing innovation and adaptation. These findings underscore the importance of a robust digital strategy and adaptive sales management in driving future growth and maintaining competitiveness in the architectural and interior design industry.

KEYWORDS: Architectural Firms, Business Growth, COVID-19 Impact, Digital Presence, Interior Design, Strategic Marketing, Sales Performance, Social Media Marketing, Sales Management.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, developments in the Interior Design Sub-Sector have shown very rapid progress. More and more people are increasingly becoming aware of the importance of aesthetics or design in an interior space, as can be evidenced by the proliferation of residences, hotels, and offices that are specially designed by professional interior designers to fit specific client needs. This is an emerging potential which can serve as a positive momentum for the rise of the Interior Design Sub-sector, and coupled along with the growth of interior design schools, studios, companies and associations, can propel this Sub-sector into the international stage. Indonesia, with its rich cultural heritage that are reflected in the country's designs, has a real chance to shine and proudly display its national identity (Niken, 2023). The interior design and Interior Design and Architecture business in Indonesia is experiencing a dynamic and exciting period, driven by a blend of tradition and modernity. The incorporation of traditional Indonesian elements, sustainable designs, modern tropical styles, smart home integration, and the seamless blending of indoor and outdoor spaces are shaping the industry's landscape. By keeping up with these trends, professionals and enthusiasts can create unique and culturally rich interiors that resonate with the country's vibrant heritage and contemporary lifestyle.

as stated by (Niken, 2023) Bogor is included in the top 5 interior design and architect firms in Indonesia, this data is supported by the National Bureau of Statistics in Indonesia report regarding the trend of the architectural and interior design firms

in number for the years of 2020-2022, or in a three years period. Despite being the top five in the industry, recently interior design firms faced a challenge for an emerging competitor in the related business fields as interior design is a specialized field that requires a deep understanding of technical knowledge, spatial planning, material selection, and building codes. Professional architects and interior designers undergo rigorous education and training to develop a comprehensive skill set and an eye for detail. On the other hand, Pinterest users who lack formal education in interior design may attempt to design spaces solely based on visual inspiration without fully considering the practical aspects and functional requirements.

Considering the rising problem of customer acquisition by the competitors that is coping with the vast digitalization of business, it is expected that we will find a suitable strategy for PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera by creating a marketing strategy on this research design and understanding the behaviour of the customer itself,

METHODS

The Research starts by conducting a problem identification of PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera, after the problem is identified we are continuing to do a business issue exploration by defining the key problem that is related and relevant theories to tackle the problem. After the problem are already defined, and the objectives are already set, Researchers do an external analysis of the competitors around and do a comparative study with the literature. The data collection process refers to the process of collecting the required data. The data collection in this research started with secondary data collection from outside the company database such as social media presence report, customer engagement report, and other relevant statistics from the competitor companies and then followed by a comparative analysis with published literature and journals from online sources. After secondary data collection, qualitative research is conducted to obtain the primary data, in this research sufficient information would be gathered through individuals or company competitors. Competitor analysis involves a comprehensive approach, including insights from interviews with PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera owner with the question “*Could you identify PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera's key competitors in the Interior Design firms industry, and what sets you apart from them in terms of product offerings and market positioning?*”; also doing online research, and social media competitors. Through this method, we identify and launch key competitors, their product offerings, pricing strategies, locations, marketing and branding efforts. This data provides valuable insight into the competitive landscape, allowing us to determine opportunities for differentiation and marketing mix improvements to improve Interior Design firm's market position and strategic direction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Social Media Presence

Table 1. Direct Competitor overall digital presence (Socialblade,2024)

Username	Followers	Engagement Rate	Active Date	Average Interactions
@rumah_aila	107K	0,26%	April 2019	76.69/ Post
@nayla.bohoscandi	129K	0,46%	March 2014	55.88 /Post
@haykaylea_hums	24K	0,88%	March 2019	78.80/ Post
@nibidesign_id	320	0%	August 2022	0 / post

As detailed in Table I.2, the digital presence of PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera's competitors is critically analyzed. The leading competitor, @nayla.bohoscandi, boasts a substantial follower count of 129,000, coupled with an engagement rate of 0.46%. This translates to an average of 55.88 interactions per post, highlighting a highly engaged follower base. The second competitor, @haykaylea_hums, has 24,000 followers and a higher engagement rate of 0.88%, averaging 78.80 interactions per post, which signifies an even more active and interactive follower base. In third place, @rumah_aila has 107,000 followers with an engagement rate of 0.26%, averaging 76.69 interactions per post. These metrics provide a comparative view that clearly indicates PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera's relatively weaker digital engagement, suggesting a delayed approach toward digitization and social media

presence. Understanding sales management practices is vital for achieving high levels of effectiveness within sales organizations (Parvien et al., 2013). The ability to identify factors linked with superior salesperson performance is crucial for enhancing the practice of sales management, thereby increasing a company's competitive edge (Román & Rodríguez, 2015). Empirical research has shown that salesperson performance significantly impacts various critical business metrics, including sales volume, productivity, customer loyalty, and unexpected expenses (Bučiūnienė & Škudienė, 2008). Moreover, Miao and Evans (2013) underscore the importance of salesperson performance in business organizations due to their role in handling essential financial, product, and customer information, which can be easily transferred from one organization to another.

Rodriguez et al. (2012) posit that effective salesperson performance must include the ability to capture granular data on potential customers. This enables a deeper understanding of customer needs, identification of key purchase influences, and comprehension of their buying process. Once such detailed data is acquired, the subsequent challenge lies in qualifying these prospects accurately.

Furthermore, the digital presence of a company significantly influences its market competitiveness. Research indicates that companies with a strong digital presence tend to have higher customer engagement, which correlates with better sales performance (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). The disparity in digital presence between PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera and its competitors points to a critical gap. Competitors with higher engagement rates, such as @nayla.bohoscandi and @haykaylea_hums, have established robust digital strategies that enhance their market positioning and customer interactions (Hoffman & Fodor, 2010). The theoretical framework of digital marketing emphasizes the importance of engagement metrics in understanding customer behavior and improving sales outcomes (Ashley & Tuten, 2015). Companies that excel in digital engagement are better positioned to drive sales growth and maintain customer loyalty. This is particularly relevant in the context of PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera, where a lag in digital engagement could be detrimental to its competitive standing.

To address these challenges, PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera must adopt a comprehensive digital strategy. This includes enhancing its social media presence, increasing follower engagement, and leveraging digital marketing tools to capture and analyze customer data effectively. By aligning its digital strategy with best practices in sales management, PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera can bridge the gap with its competitors and improve its overall market performance. In conclusion, the current digital presence of PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera's competitors demonstrates a significant advantage in terms of follower engagement and interaction. This disparity underscores the need for PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera to enhance its digital strategy to remain competitive. Integrating insights from sales management research and digital marketing frameworks can provide a robust foundation for improving its digital presence and, consequently, its sales performance.

B. Competitor Analysis

Table 2. Competitor Analysis of Interior Design Industry

Company	Primacon.Gallery	Nayla.Bohoscandi	Haykaylea_Humz	Rumah_Aila
Location	Bogor	Bogor	Bogor	Bogor
Field	Architecture and Interior Consultant	Influencer	Influencer	Influencer
Business Scope	Bogor Area and Surroundings	Online including all area of Indonesia	Online including all area of Indonesia	Online including all area of Indonesia
Architectural Style	Classic and Modern Minimalist	Bohemian and Scandinavian	Shabby Chic	Modern Minimalist
Interior Design and Architecture Design Software	Autocad, Sketchup, Lumion	Pinterest mood board, personal preference	Pinterest mood board, personal preference	Pinterest mood board, personal preference

Product Related Interior Design and Architecture	Design Drawings, Building image rendered, 3D animation, Customize furniture, Supervision	Moodboard Design, Supervision	Moodboard Design, Supervision	Moodboard Design, Supervision
Design Price	As per discussed with the interior designer	Flat price relatively cheap	Flat price relatively cheap	Flat price relatively cheap
Market Area	Bogor	Bogor	Bogor	Bogor
Segment Market	Middle to upper class	Low class	Low class	All segment
Market Activities	Word of Mouth, Instagram, Exhibition	Word of Mouth, Instagram,	Word of Mouth, Instagram	Word of Mouth, Instagram

PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera (Primacon Gallery) is an established architectural and interior consultancy firm based in Bogor, Indonesia. The company specializes in classic architectural styles and employs advanced design software such as AutoCAD, SketchUp, and Lumion. Primacon Gallery offers a comprehensive suite of services, including design drawings, building image rendering, 3D animation, customized furniture design, and project supervision. Their target market comprises middle to upper-class clients within the Bogor area, reflecting their premium service offerings. Marketing efforts include word-of-mouth promotion, an active Instagram presence, and participation in exhibitions, which help to enhance their visibility and attract high-end clientele. The company adopts a flexible pricing model based on individual consultations with interior designers, allowing for tailored solutions that cater to the specific needs and budgets of their clients.

Strengths of Primacon.Gallery:

- Professional Expertise** The use of advanced design software allows Primacon Gallery to deliver high-quality, precise, and professional design services, distinguishing it from competitors who may rely on less sophisticated tools.
- Comprehensive Service Offerings** The wide range of services provided, from initial design to project supervision and customized furniture, ensures that clients receive holistic and integrated solutions.
- Target Market Focus** By targeting middle to upper-class clients, Primacon.Gallery aligns its service offerings with the expectations and demands of a premium market segment.
- Diverse Marketing Strategies** The combination of word-of-mouth, social media engagement, and participation in exhibitions provides a multifaceted approach to marketing that enhances brand visibility and credibility.

Weaknesses of Primacon.Gallery

- Geographic Limitation** The focus on the Bogor area and its surroundings limits the company’s market reach and potential growth opportunities compared to competitors with a nationwide presence.
- Pricing Flexibility:** While flexible pricing can be advantageous, it may also deter price-sensitive customers who prefer the transparency and simplicity of flat-rate services offered by competitors.

Opportunities of Primacon.Gallery

- Expansion Beyond Bogor:** By extending services to nearby cities or even a nationwide reach, Primacon.Gallery can attract a larger clientele and increase its market share.
- Partnerships with Influencers:** Collaborating with popular influencers like Nayla.Bohoscandi, Haykaylea-Humz, and Rumah_Aila can enhance brand visibility and credibility, tapping into their extensive online audiences.
- E-commerce Integration:** Developing an online platform to showcase and sell design services or custom furniture can cater to a broader audience and simplify client engagement.
- Sustainable Design Trends:** Leveraging the growing demand for sustainable and eco-friendly design practices can position Primacon.Gallery as a leader in environmentally conscious architecture and interior design.

5. **Corporate and Commercial Projects:** Diversifying into corporate and commercial design projects can open new revenue streams and establish the firm in different market segments.

Threats of Primacon.Gallery

1. **Competition from Influencers:** Influencers like Nayla.Bohoscandi, Haykaylea_Humz, and Rumah_Aila, offering interior design services at relatively lower prices, can attract budget-conscious clients, posing a competitive threat.
2. **Economic Downturns:** Economic instability or downturns can reduce client spending on high-end architectural and interior design services, affecting revenue.
3. **Rapid Technological Changes:** Keeping up with the fast-paced advancements in design technology and software requires continuous investment in training and resources.
4. **Market Saturation:** The interior design and architecture market may become saturated with competitors offering similar services, making it challenging to stand out and attract clients.
5. **Client Preferences Shifts:** Changes in client preferences towards new architectural and design trends could require significant adjustments in service offerings and expertise.

PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera (Primacon.Gallery) has established itself as a leading architectural and interior consultancy firm in Bogor, Indonesia, renowned for its expertise in classic architectural styles and comprehensive design services. The company's strategic use of advanced design software such as AutoCAD, SketchUp, and Lumion, coupled with its wide range of services including design drawings, building image rendering, 3D animation, customized furniture design, and project supervision, positions it uniquely in the market. These strengths are further reinforced by a targeted marketing strategy that leverages word-of-mouth, a robust Instagram presence, and active participation in exhibitions, thereby enhancing its brand visibility and appeal to the middle to upper-class clientele in the Bogor area.

However, despite these strengths, Primacon.Gallery faces significant challenges. The geographic limitation to the Bogor area restricts its market reach and growth potential compared to competitors with a nationwide presence. Additionally, the flexible pricing model, while beneficial for customization, may deter price-sensitive customers who favor the simplicity and transparency of flat-rate services offered by competitors. Opportunities for expansion abound. Primacon.Gallery could explore geographic diversification beyond Bogor, potentially tapping into broader regional or national markets. Strategic partnerships with influencers such as Nayla.Bohoscandi, Haykaylea_Humz, and Rumah_Aila could significantly enhance brand visibility and attract a larger audience through their established online presence. Furthermore, integrating e-commerce capabilities to showcase and sell design services or custom furniture could streamline client engagement and broaden market reach. Embracing sustainable design trends could also position Primacon.Gallery as a pioneer in environmentally conscious architecture and interior design, appealing to the growing demographic of eco-conscious consumers. Additionally, diversifying into corporate and commercial projects could unlock new revenue streams and diversify the company's market presence. Nevertheless, Primacon.Gallery must navigate several threats. The increasing competition from influencers offering lower-priced services could erode its market share among budget-conscious clients. Economic downturns could dampen client spending on premium design services, impacting revenue streams. The rapid pace of technological advancements in design software necessitates continuous investment in training and technology upgrades to maintain its competitive edge. Moreover, market saturation in the interior design sector could make it challenging to distinguish itself from competitors offering similar services. Shifts in client preferences towards new architectural and design trends could require significant adjustments in service offerings and expertise, demanding ongoing innovation and adaptation.

In conclusion, while PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera (Primacon.Gallery) possesses a robust foundation characterized by its professional expertise, comprehensive service offerings, and strategic marketing, it must strategically address its geographic limitations and pricing flexibility. By capitalizing on emerging opportunities and mitigating potential threats, Primacon.Gallery can enhance its market position, drive sustainable growth, and maintain its status as a leader in the architectural and interior design industry in Bogor and beyond. The company's ability to innovate, adapt to market trends, and expand its service offerings will be critical in sustaining its competitive advantage and achieving long-term success.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study reveals that PT Primacon Mahatama Sejahtera's sales performance has been significantly influenced by external factors, notably the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to a sharp decline in project numbers from a peak in 2018 to a dramatic drop in 2020, resulting in stagnant sales in subsequent years. A detailed competitor analysis indicates a substantial gap in digital presence, with competitors like @nayla.bohoscandi and @haykaylea_hums achieving significantly higher engagement rates and follower interactions, underscoring the necessity for PT Primacon to enhance its digital marketing efforts. The rise of social media influencers who adeptly convert online engagement into actual consumer behavior highlights the shifting market dynamics. To address these challenges, PT Primacon must implement a comprehensive digital marketing strategy, leveraging social media analytics, increasing interactive content, and possibly collaborating with influencers to recapture market share. Additionally, refining sales management practices by understanding factors linked to superior performance, capturing detailed customer data, and adapting sales strategies to evolving consumer preferences is imperative. This strategic approach is crucial for PT Primacon to enhance its competitiveness, drive future growth, and effectively navigate the rapidly evolving architectural and interior design market landscape.

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